

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF THE USE OF LIBRARY RESOURCES AND SERVICES AMONG POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS IN SELECTED UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the use of library resources and services among postgraduate students in selected universities in Nigeria, recognising the vital role these resources play in postgraduate studies. Despite the significance of library resources and services, literature indicates suboptimal use among postgraduates students in Nigeria. The research employed a probability sampling technique to select 450 students from three universities. Data was collected through a questionnaire designed based on the study's objectives and research questions, demonstrating good reliability of 0.853 (85.3%) for library resources and 0.846 (84.6%) for library services. Findings revealed that textbooks (2.96%) and periodicals (2.75%) were the primary resources used, with journals (3.64%) and e-books (3.63%) being frequently used. Popularly used library services included Wi-Fi (3.19%) and current awareness services (3.17%) with literature search (2.85%) and reference services (2.84%), being frequent. The study emphasised the importance of leveraging library resources and services to support academic goals in postgraduate studies. The study, therefore, recommended that provision and preservation of library resources should be

given more attention in the universities, while library services should be improved upon for better service delivery.

Keywords: *Use, Library Resources, Library Services, Postgraduate Students, Nigeria*

Introduction

Libraries play a crucial role in supporting teaching, learning, and research activities in higher institutions of learning. They are essential for providing quality, diverse, and up-to-date resources and services that align with the institution's mission and goals. In any tertiary institution, the library is considered as the nerve centre and, therefore, a very crucial facility of the institution (Mason, 2010). However, in Nigeria, universities are struggling to meet the demands of the 21st century due to some factors such as population growth, inadequate library facilities, limited resources and services, insufficient funding, among others. Hence, Nigerian universities must prioritise the availability of adequate library resources and services to support the intellectual, cultural, and technical development of their students. The role of the library is to make available organised resources that will enable the university to achieve its set objectives. Library resource availability, accessibility, and use are crucial factors in knowledge acquisition, learning, and research of postgraduate students.

The rapid growth of information in today's age has significant implications for the education and library usage of patrons, including postgraduate students. Every library, regardless of its size, is expected to have adequate resources to meet its community's reading, learning, and research needs. Popoola (2008) asserted that the

information resources and services within institutional information systems should support research activities for students and faculty members. Research credibility and quality are key criteria for libraries to establish themselves as respected members of the global intellectual community. This includes research conducted by postgraduate students, which plays a crucial role in shaping the institutional repository. Utilising library resources effectively is essential for successful research endeavours, facilitating learning, teaching, and research outcomes. Libraries cater for undergraduates, postgraduates, lecturers, and the university community at large, with the quality of a university often reflected in the quality of its library resources and services. Research activities expose postgraduate students and lecturers to up-to-date information resources, as well as enhance their academic pursuits.

The importance of studies on the use of library resources and services by students in the Nigerian universities cannot be overemphasised. Since the turn of the millennium, universities and Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TeTFund) have heavily invested in library facilities, promoting increased student engagement with these resources to enrich teaching, learning, and research quality (Musa & Tsafe, 2019). To evaluate the impact of these investments on academic performance, especially among postgraduate students, studies such as this are crucial. Similarly,

such studies would identify areas where pedagogical adjustments are necessary to maximise the use of library resources, including the services in Nigerian universities to enhance academic performance. This study would guide decisions on potential additional resources required by universities to solidify the benefits derived from utilising library resources for academic purposes. Moreover, universities may be encouraged to develop a comprehensive library use policy integrating its utilisation across all academic programmes. Ultimately, this study would aid Nigerian universities in making informed decisions regarding future investments in library facilities.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the provision of library resources and services to support research activities among postgraduate students in Nigeria, there is a noticeable underutilisation of these resources and services. This is evidenced by the lack of optimal use as shown in literature, similarly observed, is the frequent requests for assistance from library staff, and the inability of many postgraduates to incorporate sufficient literature support in their research papers. Postgraduate students may be facing challenges in effectively utilising available library resources and services. This lack of engagement raises concerns as quality research heavily relies on the effective utilisation of library facilities. The limited presence of postgraduate students in the library makes it difficult to assess whether the library is meeting their information needs or not. Notably, there is a dearth of comprehensive literature addressing the use

of library resources and services by postgraduate students in Nigerian universities. Hence, this study aims to address this knowledge gap by investigating the current status of postgraduate students' use of library resources and services in universities in Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the use of library resources and services among postgraduate students in some selected universities in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. find out the library resources that are available to support postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria;
2. ascertain the library services that are available to support postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria;
3. examine how frequently postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria are using library resources; and
4. find out how frequently postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria are using library services:

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the library resources available to support postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria?
2. What are the library services available to support postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria?
3. What is the frequency of use of library resources by postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria?

4. What is the frequency of use of library services by postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria?

Literature review

The library philosophy revolves around providing users with relevant materials as resources. In a broader sense, library resources extend beyond the collections and information sources of the library, it encompasses all facilities, personnel, and financial resources that facilitate the availability and accessibility of library resources to users (Yeboah, Adams, & Boakye, 2018). Ajiboye et al., (2023) viewed library resources as materials (information resources), facilities, personnel, functions, or activities of a library intended to assist users in meeting their information needs. Library facilities, such as accommodation, library furniture, and ICT tools, are essential physical components. In academic environments, library resources play a vital role in achieving institutional goals. Oyewusi and Oyeboade (2009) suggested that the quality of an institution can be gauged by its library resources, which are crucial for supporting teaching, learning, and research. Simmonds (2001) cited in Adeniran (2011) emphasised the importance of academic libraries, providing ample materials to support institutional activities. The physical infrastructure of academic libraries, including the building, furniture, temperature control, lighting, computers, and internet access, facilitates information access and enhances user satisfaction. Insufficient library facilities can disrupt operations and affect user contentment (Alomari et al., 2023).

A study by Onuoha et al., (2013) at the Babcock University, Ilisan, identified inadequate physical facilities as a major issue in departmental libraries. Philip and Udo (2020), propose that enhancing the academic library environment can significantly improve user satisfaction. Academic libraries play a crucial role in building library collections that support teaching, learning, and research within their institutions. Library collections need to align with the information needs of their users. Mason (2010) suggests that the core mission of an academic library is to develop and manage diverse collections that meet the educational requirements of the institution. He emphasised that academic libraries should offer access to a wide range of information resources. Traditionally, library collections consisted mainly of print materials such as books, manuscripts, textbooks, newspapers, maps, magazines, and printed journals, as noted by Nzivo (2012). However, the rapid advancement of information technology has compelled academic libraries to expand their collection development beyond traditional print materials to include electronic resources as well.

Popoola and Haliso (2009) defined library resources as information materials available in both print and electronic formats, including textbooks, journals, indexes, abstracts, newspapers, magazines, reports, CD-ROM databases, Internet/email, videotapes, cassettes, diskettes, magnetic disks, computers, microforms, and more. These materials are the foundation that libraries acquire, catalogue, store, and provide to their users. Okiki (2013) argued

that a well-equipped library should offer a wide range of books and periodicals across various subjects to support advanced study and research. Likewise, Bola (2013) posits that the primary role of a library is to gather, organise, and distribute information to postgraduate students, supporting in the creation of new knowledge.

According to Okwu and Braide (2021), postgraduate students highly value certain key library resources. These include the institutional library as a convenient research location, a place to access current printed publications, a quiet space for individual study, and a hub for modern IT equipment and digital resources. The study pointed out a lack of understanding among many postgraduate students and researchers regarding the library's role in their research activities. As a result, the study recommended that the library take proactive measures to promote itself within the institution, ensuring that its value is recognised by all.

On the other hand, evaluating library services is essential as a management tool to assess the library's effectiveness in meeting user needs, recognising service shortcomings, and proposing improvements (Oyewusi & Oyeboade, 2009). Moreover, according to Olayemi (2020), User contentment is influenced by many factors, such as the library's size, collection, material organisation, catalogue utility, staff collaboration in assisting users, and ensuring users are exposed to resources and additional library services. Assessing library services should be seen as a management tool used to

evaluate how effectively and efficiently the library meets user needs, identifies service limitations and failures, and suggest ways to enhance service (Agboola et al., 2019). Service quality is determined by the extent to which the service provided aligns with user expectations. Consistently meeting user expectations is key to delivering quality service, which determines the success of the library as a service organisation in providing high-quality services.

Postgraduate students are considered mature due to their advancement beyond undergraduate studies, they constitute a significant user group within university libraries. Despite this, Rasul and Singh (2010) noted a lack of adequate literature addressing the information needs of postgraduate students. Understanding how these students perceive the role of their university library is crucial, given the independent nature of postgraduate studies. The author suggested that access to library services is vital for postgraduates to achieve their academic goals. Olofinsawe and Oyeniya (2010) emphasised the necessity for academic libraries to develop comprehensive physical and digital information collections to meet the knowledge needs of users, particularly postgraduate students. Hence, policy planning in university libraries should prioritise the unique needs of postgraduate students.

Research Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A probability sampling technique was employed to select the respondents. The study aimed for a

representative population sample through a multi-stage sampling method. In the first stage, three geopolitical zones in the country were randomly selected: Southwest, North Central, and South-South. Subsequently, three universities were randomly chosen from each of these selected zones, namely, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Oyo State (Southwest); University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State (North Central); and Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State (South-South). In the final sampling stage, 150 students were randomly selected from each of the three universities, resulting in a total sample size of 450 students. For data collection, a self-developed questionnaire derived from the study's specific objectives

and research questions was used. Before administration, the questionnaire was subjected to both face and content validity checks, and a pilot study was conducted to standardise the research instrument. The questionnaire was divided into three sections. Section A demanded the respondents' demographic information on gender, age, marital status, level, and stage of study. Section B focused on resources available in the library, while Section C examined services offered by the library. Out of the 450 copies of the questionnaires administered, 383 adequately filled copies were returned and deemed valid for data analysis. The collected data underwent analysis using descriptive statistics, percentages, frequencies, mean, and standard deviation.

Table 1: Demographic distribution of the respondents

Variables		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Gender	Male	184	48.1	48.1
	Female	199	51.9	100
	Total	383	100	
Age	Less than 20	8	2.1	2.1
	20-25	46	12.0	14.1
	26-30	111	29.0	43.1
	31-35	140	36.6	79.7
	36 and above	78	20.4	100
	Total	383	100	
Marital Status	Single	178	46.5	46.5
	Married	193	50.4	96.9
	Divorced	6	1.6	98.5
	Widowed	6	1.5	100
	Total	383	100.0	
Level of Study	Master	214	55.9	55.9
	M.Phil	74	19.3	75.2
	Ph.D	95	24.8	100
	Total	383	100	
Stage of Study	Coursework	178	46.5	46.5
	Prefield/Postfield	205	53.5	100
	Total	383	100	

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 1 presents an overview of respondents' demographic distribution. The table shows that 199 (51.9%) were female, while 184 (48.1%) were male. This distribution demonstrated a substantial participation from female respondents relative to their male counterparts. The data also indicated that a significant portion of the respondents were married 193 (50.4%), while 178 (46.5) were single. Based on the level of study, a total of 214 (55.9%) respondents were studying at the Master's level, 74 (19.3%) at the M.Phil level, and the remaining 95 (24.8%) were at Ph.D. level. In addition, the age distribution of the respondents varied: 46 participants (12.0%) fell within the 20-25 age bracket, 111 (29.0%) were aged 26-30, 140 (36.6%) were between 31-35 years old, and 78 (20.4%) were 36 years old or older. In terms of academic engagement, 178 (46.5%) of the postgraduate students were engaged in full coursework, while 205 (53.5%) were focused on writing their thesis or dissertation.

Research question one: What are the library resources available to support postgraduate students in the universities in Nigeria?

Table 2: Library resources available to support postgraduate students

S/N	Library Resources	A	NS	NA	X	SD
1	Textbooks	367 (95.8%)	9 (2.3%)	7 (1.8%)	2.96	0.24
2	E-Books	324 (84.6%)	22 (5.7%)	37 (9.7%)	2.75	0.63
3	Search engines	317 (82.8%)	24 (6.3%)	42 (11.0%)	2.72	0.66
4	World Wide Web	335 (87.5%)	15 (3.9%)	33 (8.6%)	2.79	0.58
5	Government Publications	308 (80.4%)	29 (7.6%)	46 (12.0%)	2.68	0.66
6	Periodicals (Journals, Newspapers, Reports, and Magazines)	323 (84.3%)	24 (6.3%)	36 (9.4%)	2.75	0.63
7	Online Catalogue	307 (80.2%)	24 (6.3%)	52 (13.6%)	2.67	0.70
8	Electronic Databases (Hinari, Agora, Ebschost, Science direct)	301 (78.6%)	33 (8.6%)	59 (15.4%)	2.68	0.74
9	CD-ROMs	249 (65.0%)	60 (15.6%)	84 (21.9%)	2.48	0.87
10	Online indexes	292 (76.2%)	33 (8.6%)	58 (15.1%)	2.61	0.74
11	Reserve Books and Videos	265 (69.2%)	35 (9.1%)	83 (21.7%)	2.48	0.85
12	Brain Fuse	109 (28.5%)	66 (17.2%)	208 (54.3%)	1.74	0.83
13	Indexes	304 (79.4%)	27 (7.0%)	52 (13.6%)	2.66	0.72
14	Computers files	288 (75.2%)	33 (8.6%)	62 (16.2%)	2.59	0.73
15	Microform.	125 (32.6%)	57 (14.9%)	201 (52.5%)	1.80	0.84
Weighted Mean = 2.56						

Key: A= Available, NS= Not Sure, NA= Not Available, X= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey 2024

To identify the library resources that support postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria, respondents were asked to indicate the level of agreement or disagreement with 15 items on library resources. The results presented in Table 2 show that a three-point Likert scale classified into available, not sure, and not available were used to elicit information from the respondents. Textbook (2.96) was ranked the highest by the mean score as the major library resource available to support postgraduate students' academic pursuits. It was followed by Periodicals (Journals, Newspapers, Reports, and Magazines) (2.75) and E-Books (2.75) while Brain Fuse (1.74) was the least item indicated by the respondents.

Research question Two: What are the library services available to support postgraduate students in the universities in Nigeria?

Table 3: Library services available to support postgraduate students

S/N	Library Services	A	NS	NA	X	SD
1	Current Awareness	273 (70.1%)	29 (7.6%)	81 (21.1%)	2.50	0.82
2	Literature search	349 (91.1%)	13 (3.4%)	21 (5.5%)	2.85	0.48
3	Lending service	313 (81.7%)	16 (4.2%)	54 (14.1%)	2.67	0.73
5	Reservation service	300 (78.3%)	22 (5.7%)	61 (15.9%)	2.62	0.75
6	User Education	303 (79.1%)	15 (3.9%)	65 (17.0%)	2.62	0.76
7	Referral Service	296 (77.3%)	20 (5.2%)	67 (17.5%)	2.59	0.78
8	Indexing and abstracting service	292 (76.2%)	26 (6.8%)	65 (17.0%)	2.59	0.77
9	Exhibition and displays	270 (70.5%)	30 (7.8%)	83 (21.7%)	2.48	0.84
10	Reference service	353 (92.2%)	5 (1.3%)	25 (6.5%)	2.84	0.52
11	Wi-Fi service	314 (82.0%)	21 (5.5%)	48 (12.5%)	2.69	0.68
12	Online research service	320 (83.6%)	33 (8.6%)	30 (7.8%)	2.75	0.57
13	Multimedia service	294 (76.8%)	23 (6.0%)	66 (17.2%)	2.53	0.77
14	Electronic document delivery	259 (66.9%)	37 (9.7%)	87 (22.7%)	2.44	0.85
15	Bindery	277 (72.3%)	34 (8.9%)	72 (18.8%)	2.53	0.82
16	Selective Dissemination of Information	252 (65.8%)	32 (8.4%)	99 (25.8%)	2.39	0.86
17	Reprographic service	253 (66.1%)	32 (8.4%)	98 (25.6%)	2.32	0.89
18	CD/DVD-based search service	214 (55.9%)	43 (11.2%)	126 (32.9%)	2.22	0.92
19	Inter-library loan	234 (61.1%)	42 (11.0%)	107 (27.9%)	2.33	0.84
20	Translation service	244 (63.7%)	41 (10.7%)	98 (25.6%)	2.38	0.88
Weighted Mean = 2.56						

Key: A= Available, NS= Not Sure, NA= Not Available, X= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey 2024

To identify library services supporting postgraduate students' research in the Nigerian universities, respondents rated the availability of various services. The results, shown in Table 3 indicate that literature search (2.85) was ranked the top library service supporting postgraduate research, followed by reference service (2.84) and online research service (2.75). CD/DVD-based search service (2.22) was the least favoured service.

Research question three: What is the frequency of use of library resources for research activities by postgraduate students in the universities in Nigeria?

Table 4: Frequency of use of library resources by postgraduate students

S/N	Frequency of use of library resources	VHF	HF	LF	VLF	X	SD
1	Textbooks	262 68.4%	103 26.9%	13 3.4%	5 1.3%	3.63	0.64
2	E-books	197 51.4%	136 35.5%	36 9.4%	14 3.7%	3.35	0.84
3	Dictionaries	165 43.0%	133 34.7%	58 15.1%	27 6.9%	3.14	0.94
4	Journals	268 69.9%	98 25.6%	11 2.9%	6 1.6%	3.64	0.68
5	Encyclopedia	153 39.9%	156 40.7%	52 13.6%	18 4.7%	3.14	0.87
6	Reserve Books and Videos	135 35.2%	155 40.5%	68 17.7%	25 6.5%	3.04	0.83
7	Microform	61 15.9%	87 22.7%	112 29.2%	123 32.1%	2.22	1.02
8	Brain Fuse	63 16.4%	88 22.9%	114 29.8%	118 30.8%	2.25	1.03
9	Electronic Databases (Hinari, Agora, Ebschost, and Science Direct)	190 49.6%	154 40.2%	27 6.9%	12 3.1%	3.36	0.74
10	Government Publications	142 37.1%	137 35.8%	66 17.2%	38 9.9%	3.00	0.97
Weighted Mean = 3.08							

Key: VHF= Very High Frequency, HF= High Frequency, LF= Less Frequency, VLF= Very Less Frequency, X=Mean SD= Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey 2024

To ascertain the usage frequency of library resources by postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria, the respondents were asked to rate their degree of agreement with the ten items on the frequency of use of library resources. Table 4 reveals that journals (3.64) received the highest mean score, followed by Textbooks (3.63) and electronic databases (3.36). Microform (2.22) was the least ranked resource by the respondents

Research question four: What is the frequency of use of library services by postgraduate students in the universities in Nigeria?

Table 5: Frequency of use of library services by postgraduate students

S/N	Frequency of use of library services	VHF	HF	LF	VLF	X	SD
1	User Education	141 36.8%	165 43.1%	57 14.9%	20 5.2%	3.11	0.84
2	Wi-Fi service	182 47.5%	126 32.9%	39 10.2%	36 9.4%	3.19	0.97
3	Lending service	142 37.1%	137 35.8%	80 20.9%	24 6.3%	3.04	0.93
4	Referral Service	129 33.7%	153 39.9%	76 19.8%	25 6.5%	3.01	0.90
5	Current awareness service	154 40.2%	159 41.5%	50 13.1%	20 5.2%	3.17	0.84
6	Inter-library loan	107 27.9%	133 34.7%	106 27.7%	37 9.7%	2.81	0.95
7	Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI)	118 30.8%	159 41.5%	72 18.8%	34 8.9%	2.94	0.96
8	Reprographic service	162 42.3%	118 30.8%	68 17.8%	35 9.1%	3.06	0.98
9	Indexes and abstract	149 38.9%	129 33.7%	72 18.8%	33 8.6%	3.02	0.99
10	Exhibition and displays	126 32.3%	142 37.1%	84 21.9%	31 8.1%	2.95	0.94
Weighted Mean = 3.03							

Key: VHF= Very High Frequency, HF= High Frequency, LF= Less Frequency, VLF= Very Less Frequency, X=Mean SD= Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey 2024

To determine the frequency of use of library services by postgraduate students in universities in Nigeria, participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with the ten items related to their use of library services. The results in Table 5 reveal that Wi-Fi service (3.19) received the highest mean score, followed by Current awareness service (3.17) and User education (3.11). Selective Dissemination of Information (2.94) was the least-ranked service by the respondents.

Discussion of the findings

These findings are consistent with Edem and Egbe (2016), who noted that online databases are the most frequently accessed library materials, followed by dictionaries, books, and encyclopedias, with CD-ROM databases

being the least utilised. Adeniran (2011) highlighted the increasing emphasis among academic librarians on delivering high-quality services, viewing the library as a provider of service quality and access rather than solely a physical space. The evolving

role of technology and automation has transformed perceptions of people about libraries.

Furthermore, Oyewusi and Oyeboade (2009) emphasised the importance of guidance in utilising library resources and services, highlighting the necessity of user education programmes in assisting students towards meeting their information requirements. This aligns with the assertion by Musa and Tsafe, (2019) that library services play a pivotal role in fostering self-development, organisational development, and national progress, serving as educational catalysts. The provision of library services holds significant importance for universities due to its direct impact on enhancing productivity. These findings are consistent with Popoola and Haliso (2009), who emphasised that library resources, available in both printed and electronic formats, encompass textbooks, journals, indexes, abstracts, newspapers, magazines, reports, and CD-ROM. Among others are

databases, the Internet/E-mail, videotapes/cassettes, diskettes, magnetic disks, computers, and microforms. In addition to this, Agboola et al., (2019) asserted that resources such as textbooks, journals, and e-books found in university libraries, archives, records offices, documentation centres, and data centres are intended to support research output.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that high-quality library resources and services are crucial for the academic success of postgraduate students. Despite inevitable challenges, the use of library resources and services significantly impacts the accomplishments of postgraduate students in their research pursuits. This underscores the importance of continued investment in library resources and services by university administrations to support the academic pursuits of postgraduate students in Nigerian universities.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Conduct regular surveys to gather feedback from postgraduate students and continually improve library resources and services based on their needs.
2. The library should conduct regular seminars for newly enrolled postgraduate students on the efficient utilisation of existing library resources and services for research purposes.
3. Implement regular training sessions for postgraduate students on the effective utilisation of library resources and services for their research activities.
4. Enhance Internet connectivity within the library premises to ensure seamless access to online resources for postgraduate students.

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